

The Dynamics Of Miners' Movements Analyzed

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Abstract: The article analyzes the necessary information on the condition of workers and the types of movement and the dynamics of their movement when choosing the constructive parameters of miners' work clothes.

Keywords — mining, metallurgy, miners, research, special clothing, intensive, aesthetic, design, ergonomic, design, operation.

INTRODUCTION.

In order to analyze the dynamics of movements, it was carried out during the daily work planned in the work shift at the Navoi Mine Metallurgical Combine in the city of Navoi, Republic of Uzbekistan. The study consisted of studying the condition and types of movement of underground and surface mining workers. As a result of the research, uncharacteristic actions were excluded and more frequent actions were included (Table 1).[1]

Working positions and actions of miners performed during the work process

The analysis of the movements performed by the miners and the movement charts of the working day allowed to identify the main characteristic movements determined by the greatest intensity and amplitude (Picture 1).[2]

Picture 1. Analysis of the types of actions of miners that are often performed during the work process

The main ergonomic requirement for the design and the decisive factor in choosing the structural parameters of miners' work clothes is to ensure its dynamic compatibility with the characteristic and extreme movements of the worker in certain conditions. In the past, with the large number of basic joint constructions of miners, it has been found that their use in the design of work clothes for miners is not effective, because they do not take into account the nature of the main work movement. Designed for surface and underground miners to guarantee a minimum level of restriction of freedom of movement to the worker.[3]

As a result of the analysis of characteristic movements, the main dimensional characteristics that ensure dynamic growth were determined. The object of the study was a group of surface and underground workers aged 25 to 45 years. The sample size was 50 people. Permissible deviations in repeated measurements are 2-3 mm, the repetition of measurements is equal to 3.

With the working movements of underground and surface workers, the distances between individual points of the body measured along its surface change. Therefore, it is necessary to measure the values of the same dimensional properties in static and dynamic, and calculate the dynamic effect that shows the difference between them.

Picture 2. Maximum flexion of dynamic movement.

Table 2 shows the dynamic gains and effects of selected dimensional characteristics of the male figure depending on the complex values of the amplitude angles of the movements.

Indicators of dynamic effects

2-table.

№	Determination of dimensional properties	The value of dimensional properties		Dynamic growth	Dynamic effect, %
		in statics	in dynamics		
1	Og2	104	106,2	2,2	2.3
2	Vprz	20	23	3	0.6
3	DTS	44	50	6	2.7
4	Osh	45	46,5	1,5	0.7
5	From.br	102	106	4	4.08
6	Shs	42	44	6	2.52
7	Ob	107	112	5	5.35
8	Ds	28	33	5	9.24
9	Dn	74	80	6	4.44
10	Knee circumference	40	54	14	5.6
11	Elbow circumference	27	42	15	4.05

The obtained relationships between dynamic effects and angular parameters of movements allow the use of angular biomechanical parameters as initial data to target dynamic compliance in clothing design.[4]

Requirements for miners' clothing are as follows:

social indicators, the suitability of special-purpose items to the requirements, competitiveness in the domestic and foreign markets, the suitability of the clothing to the consumer's needs in terms of height and size assortment;

indicators of hygienic suitability - should characterize their compliance with sanitary and hygiene norms and provide a comfortable microclimate under clothing;

aesthetic indicators - compatibility with modern style and fashion;

operational indicator - an indicator of the reliability of clothing in the period of operation, the shape retention and durability of details;

ergonomic indicators indicate the level of adaptation of the product to a person;

functional indicators include clothing's suitability for the main function, size, age, and fullness group characteristics of the consumer.[5]

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